

1 **The use of differential separation and density gradient with AllGrad 90%**
2 **after thawing improves the sperm quality of South American catfish**
3 **(*Rhamdia quelen*)**

4 **Abstract**

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6 The use of technologies in assisted reproduction, such as the use of
7 centrifugation, has been reported as a tool that allows separating the best portion
8 of sperm from cryopreserved milt. The main of this work was to compare two
9 separation techniques, differential and density gradient, on thawed *Rhamdia*
10 *quelen* milt, based on sperm functionality and fertilization capacity. Three
11 treatments were compared: control, differential centrifugation or pelletization
12 (T1), and density gradient centrifugation (T2). Motility percentage was better for
13 differential ($42.58 \pm 6.50\%$) than for the control treatment ($32.44 \pm 6.03\%$).
14 Membrane integrity and kinetic parameters was not different between treatments.
15 The presence of normal sperm was higher in T2 treatment ($13.55 \pm 5.82\%$) when
16 compared to the control ($10.72 \pm 3.53\%$) and T1 ($3.97 \pm 1.95\%$). There was a
17 lower rate of morphological tail damage in the T1 ($26.91 \pm 7.13\%$) treatment
18 compared to the T2 ($37.48 \pm 10.81\%$) and control ($45.88 \pm 4.84\%$). For the head
19 morphologies, the lowest percentages were for the control ($35.72 \pm 5.89\%$) and
20 T2 ($4.89 \pm 14.94\%$) treatments compared to the T1 treatment ($62.59 \pm 9.67\%$). In
21 the MTT (3- (4, 5-dimethylthiazolyl)-2, 5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) test
22 (AU/100 million spz), the centrifuged treatments resulted in values of 1.58 ± 0.79
23 (T1) and 2.02 ± 1.88 (T2), better than the treatment control (0.20 ± 0.08).
24 Likewise, the fertilization and hatching rates, respectively, were better for the T1
25 ($76.68 \pm 15.22\%$ and $54.62 \pm 17.39\%$) and T2 ($69.85 \pm 17.85\%$ and $50.87 \pm$
26 20.59%) treatments, than the control treatment ($40.03 \pm 11.67\%$ and $24.14 \pm$
27 13.97%). The comparison of differential centrifugation with density gradient
28 centrifugation was carried out for the first time with cryopreserved milt of *R.*
29 *quelen*. In summary, both centrifugation techniques proved to be efficient in
30 obtaining a better portion of functional sperm from thawed milt. This is based on
31 the high rates of embryonic survival and hatching obtained after both differential
32 and density gradient separation.

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34 **Keywords:** Fish; Cryopreservation; Hatch; Morphology; Centrifugation

35

1. Introduction

37

38 The world production of fish was estimated at 179 million tonnes in 2018
39 with a per capita consumption of 20.5 kg, and growth of 13% is expected for the
40 year 2030. **America is** in third place, representing a 14% of the world production
41 (FAO, 2020). Brazilian fish farming reached 802,930 tons in 2020, which
42 represents an increase of 5.93% in relation to 2019, being 31.1% represented by
43 the South region (Associação Brasileira da Piscicultura, 2021). In this Region, the
44 neotropical species, *Rhamdia quelen*, has acquired great economic importance
45 due to its zootechnical and market quality, as mentioned (Amaral, 2013). It also
46 produces excellent reproductive results by responding positively to hormonal
47 induction management (Sanches et al., 2013b), proving its potential for
48 production in captivity (Gomes et al., 2000). Even so, according to CONCEA
49 (2019), it is a species that also has importance as an experimental model
50 (CONCEA, 2019), for example, for the development of new pharmacological
51 approaches (Rodrigues et al., 2019). Thus, the use of techniques of artificial
52 propagation or biotechnologies of reproduction, such as cryopreservation, is
53 fundamental when it is desired to use programs of reproduction to contribute to
54 the production and survival of offspring in fish (Sheikhi et al., 2011; Martínez-
55 Páramo et al., 2017).

56 Cryopreservation of fish gametes is considered a tool for artificial
57 reproduction and genetic improvement of aquaculture species. This
58 biotechnology involve solutions both for the maintenance of fish species used as
59 an animal model (Howe et al., 2013), and for preservation programs for the
60 endangered species (Tiersch, 2008), to implement at the industry level (Tiersch
61 and Green, 2011). Nevertheless, in the cryopreservation of fish milt, there are still
62 challenges that must be faced, such as the lack of standardization of the existing
63 cryopreservation protocols (Viveiros and Godinho, 2009; Martínez-Páramo et al.,
64 2017) , or the low quality of sperm after freeze-thaw (Xin et al., 2019). The sperm
65 quality is considered not only as the capacity of this cell to reach an oocyte and
66 fertilize it, but also to contribute to the successful initial embryonic development
67 (Cabrita et al., 2014).

68 Density gradient centrifugation has been documented for the separation of
69 different populations of male reproductive cells for various fish species, for
70 example, sterlet [*Acipenser ruthenus* (Dzyuba et al., 2014)], tench [*Tinca tinca*
71 (Linhartová et al., 2014)], Patagonian pejerrey [*Odontesthes hatcheri* (Majhi et al.,
72 2014)], blue catfish [*Ictalurus furcatus* (Shang et al., 2018)], piracanjuba [*Brycon*
73 *orbignyanus* (de Siqueira-Silva et al., 2019)], common carp [*Cyprinus carpio*
74 (Franěk et al., 2019)]. In addition, other studies have shown that density gradient
75 centrifugation technique promises to be an efficient technique for selecting the
76 sperm that best survive the cryopreservation processes. An example of this is a
77 work done with *C. carpio* (Li et al., 2010). These authors reported as being the
78 first time that the technique was used to separate sperm from fish. They
79 evaluated membrane integrity, motility, and sperm speed, showing significant
80 improvements in the separated milt. **The main of this work was to compare two
81 separation techniques, differential and density gradient with AllGrad® 90%, on
82 thawed *R. quelen* milt, based on sperm functionality and fertilization capacity.**

83 **2. Materials and methods**

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85 The Ethics Committee of the Paulista State University "Júlio de Mesquita
86 Filho" (UNESP) approved all protocols reported in this study with the Project
87 Number: 01/2021.

88 89 **2.1. Experimental framework and animals**

90 Eleven males (146.2 ± 141.7 g) and one female (872 g) *Rhamdia quelen*
91 were used in the UNESP/Registro laboratory, located at coordinates 24°31'55''S
92 and 47°51'34''W. The fish remained stocked in 10000 L geomembrane tanks, in
93 a recirculation system, until the moment of milt collection and fertilization. They
94 were fed three times a day, until apparent satiety and feeding was restricted 24
95 hours before collection of gametes to avoid contamination by feces. Female able
96 to reproduce was selected; the female exhibited a rounded abdomen, reddish
97 protruding urogenital papilla and uniform oocyte size (Bombardelli et al., 2006).
98 The males selected released milt when subjected to mild celomatic pressure
99 (Sanchez et al., 2013b).

100 101 **2.2. Gamete collection**

102 To collect the milt and oocytes, the broodstock were transferred to the
103 reproduction laboratory and weighed individually, identified, and allocated in
104 plastic tanks of 500 L, in a recirculation system equipped with aeration and a
105 temperature of 24 °C. Males were hormonally induced using a single
106 intramuscular application of 3 mg carp pituitary extract (CPE)/1 mL 0.9% NaCl
107 solution/kg body weight per male to promote spermiation (Bombardelli et al.,
108 2006; Adames et al., 2015). The oocytes were obtained at the time of fertilization.
109 To promote the final maturation and ovulation, the female was subjected to a
110 hormonal manipulation protocol by applying two intramuscular doses of CPE in
111 the dorsal region, according to protocol adapted from (Adames et al., 2015). The
112 first dose was 0.5 mg CPE/1 mL of NaCl solution 0.9%/kg body weight and eight
113 hours later, the second dose (2.5 mg CPE/1 mL). Oocytes and milt collection was
114 performed after the period corresponding to 240 degree-hours (10 h; water at 24
115 °C), counted from the application of the second hormonal dose of the female and
116 the single dose of the males (Sanches et al., 2011; Adames et al., 2015).

117 The collection of gametes was individually performed for each broodstock.
118 For males, milt was collected in graduated 15 mL Falcon tubes by abdominal
119 massage in the cephalocaudal direction. The handling of the specimens was
120 carried out with wet cloth. The urogenital area was wiped dry to prevent
121 contamination with water or mucus and the first samples of milt released were
122 discarded to avoid possible contamination with urine, mucus, feces, or water
123 (Marques et al., 2021). Immediately after milt collection, the sperm motile was
124 validated with the Computer Assisted Sperm Analysis (CASA) system (Sanches
125 et al., 2010; Sanches et al., 2013a), to detect the presence or absence of motile
126 sperm in fresh milt before forming the *pool*. Thus, samples with a motility
127 percentage of less than 65% were discarded. After collection and sperm motility
128 validation, samples were mixed to provide a milt *pool* and to minimize the
129 differences of sperm quality. The oocytes were obtained by extrusion following
130 the care already described for the males.

131 132 **2.3. Experimental design**

133 The experimental design is summarized in Fig. 1. The cryopreserved samples
134 were divided into three experimental groups or treatments (Table 1), control,
135 differential centrifugation or pelletizing (T1), and density gradient centrifugation

136 (T2). For all treatments, after thawed, concentration (n= 8 straws), sperm
137 functionality [motility and kinetic parameters by CASA (n= 8 straws), morphology
138 (n= 8 straws, each straws in duplicate), membrane integrity (n= 8 straws) and
139 mitochondrial activity (n= 8 straws)] was evaluated, as well as embryonic survival
140 (n= 8 straws, each straws in duplicate). Before milt cryopreservation and
141 immediately after forming *pool*, sperm concentration (1.21×10^{10} sperm cells/mL)
142 was measured, as well as sperm morphology [64.75 ± 0.35 % normal sperm
143 (Streit Jr et al., 2004; Bombardelli et al., 2006; Sanches et al., 2011)] and the
144 percentage of motility [76.48 ± 10.08 % (Sanches et al., 2010; Sanches et al.,
145 2013a)] by CASA, in order to know the quality of the milt *pool* to be cryopreserved.

147 [Fig.1. here]

148 [Table 1 here]

149 **2.4. Sperm cryopreservation**

151 The *pool* milt was cryopreserved following the methodology proposed by
152 Adames et al., (2015). In short, sperm was diluted at a ratio of 1:3 with the
153 cryomedium containing 5% fructose (Sigma- Aldrich®), 5% powdered milk
154 (Molico®-Nestlé) and 10% methanol (Sigma- Aldrich®). Sperm was loaded into
155 0.25 mL straws (Minitube®) which were subsequently conditioned in a canister
156 and kept in liquid nitrogen steam for 18 h (*dry-shipper* CP300, -170 °C). After that
157 time has elapsed, the straws were plunged into liquid nitrogen and stored in
158 canister. Twenty-four hours after the cryopreservation, the *R. quelen* sperm
159 samples were thawed in a 25 °C water bath for 10 s.

161 **2.5. Centrifugation and conformation of density gradient**

162 Differential treatment or pelleting (Griffith, 2010) was applied, therefore,
163 100 µL of thawed milt was mixed with 200 µL of the Ginsburg solution and was
164 then centrifuged. For gradient treatment, a density gradient (90% and 45%) was
165 formed before centrifugation using the AllGrad® 90% gradient (Catalog numbers:
166 AG90-050, AG90-100, LifeGlobal Group, Europe) and subsequently centrifuged
167 according to the methodology adapted from (Pérez-Atehortúa et al., 2021). In
168 summary, to prepare a 45% AllGrad solution, the AllGrad® 90% was mixed at a
169 1:1 ratio with Ginsburg solution (NaCl 123.2 mM, KCl 3.75 mM, CaCl₂ 3.0 mM,

170 NaHCO₃ 2.65 mM [300mOsm, pH 7.5]). One hundred microliters of 90% AllGrad
171 solution was placed into a 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube and 100 µL of 45% AllGrad
172 was smoothly layered over this. At the end of the AllGrad gradient column a layer
173 of 100 µL of thawed milt was gently placed. To place all layers within the gradient,
174 a 200 µL micropipette and tip was used. However, for the last two layers (45%
175 AllGrad solution and milt sample), a 10 µL tip was adapted to the 200 µL tip,
176 allowing it to be poured more smoothly to avoid mixing.

177 Separation of both treatments, differential and gradient, was performed by
178 centrifugation at 1000 X g for 10 min at 4 °C, in a refrigerated centrifuge (SP-
179 701/6000 Serial No.: 08/13-0001). After centrifugation, the supernatant above the
180 sperm fraction was carefully removed and the pellet material were resuspended
181 in 200 µL of Ginsburg solution. A second centrifugation was performed (500 X g
182 for 5 min at 4 °C), the supernatant was again discarded, and the pellet was
183 resuspended in 150 µL of extender solution. This sperm suspension was used to
184 carry out the analysis of sperm concentration, morphology, and fertilization
185 capacity. For the analysis of membrane integrity, some variations were made in
186 the protocol because the cell suspension needed to be concentrated in a pellet
187 to facilitate the action of the fluorescent dyes. Thus, after the first centrifugation
188 the pellet was normally resuspended, however, only 50 µL of this suspension was
189 used to perform the second centrifugation. Finally, this pellet was used for
190 analysis as explained later. To mitochondrial functionality, the pellet was not
191 diluted in Ginsburg after the second centrifugation, but in 400 µL of MTT (3-(4,
192 5-dimethylthiazolyl-2)-2, 5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) as explained later.

193 194 **2.6. Sperm concentration**

195 The sperm concentration was analyzed with the help of a Neubauer
196 chamber, with previous fixation of the sperm in saline-buffered formaldehyde
197 (Streit Jr et al., 2004; Bombardelli et al., 2006; Sanches et al., 2011). To measure
198 the sperm concentration, it was necessary to perform a prior standardization in
199 the laboratory of the sperm suspension and the fixation solution due to the
200 different number of sperm obtained in each treatment, even more so after of the
201 centrifugations. In this sense, for the control treatment a proportion of 1:999 µL
202 was used, the same as that used to measure fresh milt, and for the T1 and T2
203 treatments, the proportions were 50:450 µL and 50:150 µL, respectively. The

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204 counts were made and reading with the help of a microscope (Nikon Eclipse
205 E200, Tokyo, Japan) and a 40 x objective lens.

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207 **2.7. Assessment of sperm function**

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209 **2.7.1. Sperm motility**

210 Sperm motility was initiated with the use of distilled water, mixed in a 150 μ L
211 eppendorf tube for the control and differential treatments, and for the T2 treatment
212 it was performed directly in the Neubauer chamber, and the proportions (v:v,
213 milt:distilled water) varied according to the treatment analyzed. **Each volume was**
214 **previously standardized due to the evident decrease in the number of sperm cells**
215 **after each centrifugation.** Therefore, for control treatment a ratio of 1:100 μ L was
216 used, the same proportion used for fresh milt. The ratios of 1:50 μ L and 1:10 μ L
217 were used for T1 and T2 treatments, respectively.

218 According to the methodology adapted from (Sanches et al., 2010;
219 Sanches et al., 2013a), 10 μ L of the mixture, control and T1 treatments, were
220 placed in a mirrored Neubauer chamber. For all experimental groups a phase
221 contrast trinocular microscope Solaris Bel, planochromatic objectives and LED
222 illumination (Italian model, 20 x objective) were used. Videos were recorded from
223 5 to 50 s post-activation using a digital video camera (BALSER, acA640-120uc,
224 Germany) coupled to the microscope. All samples were analysed 5 s after
225 activation by assessment at a rate of 100 frames per second.

226 Sperm kinetics parameters were analysed with the CASA-ImageJ system
227 (U.S. National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, Maryland, USA). Briefly, the capture
228 of the videos was made in the .avi format, edited in the software VIRTUALDUB-
229 1.10.4 (<http://www.virtualdub.org/>), and exported as a sequence of images,
230 corresponding to 1 s of video, in .jpg format. Then the image sequence files were
231 imported into ImageJ 1.51j8/JAVA 1.8.0_112 (<http://imagej.nih.gov/ij>) free
232 software and analyses using the CASA plug-in (open-source software available
233 at <http://wilson-leedy.com/CASA/instructions.html>).

234 **The sperm parameters calculated by the open-source CASA were: Motility**
235 **time (s), motility percentage (MOT, %), curvilinear velocity (VCL, μ m/s), average**
236 **path velocity (VAP, μ m/s), straight-line velocity (VSL, μ m/s), straightness index**
237 **(STR, %), wobble (WOB, %), progression (PROG, μ m), and beats per seconds**

238 (BCF, beats/s). There was use of the following input variable values in the CASA
239 plugin: a= 1, b= 60, c= 50, d= 10, e= 3, f= 10, g= 20, h= 5, i= 1, j= 15, k= 10, l=
240 20, m= 80, n= 80, o= 50, p= 60, q= 100, r= 561.7978, s=0, t=0).

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242 **2.7.2. Membrane integrity**

243 The evaluation of the membrane integrity or sperm viability of the samples
244 after thawing were performed using an Accuri C6 flow cytometer (BD
245 Biosciences) equipped with a 488 nm solid state laser and a 640 nm diode laser.
246 Before measuring the membrane integrity 50 μ L of thawed milt from the control
247 treatment were also taken and subjected to a single centrifugation of 1000 X g
248 for 10 min, the supernatant was discarded, and the pellet was used for measure
249 plasma membrane integrity. This centrifugation was performed because these
250 cells are in suspension, making it necessary to concentrate them in a pellet and
251 facilitating the actions of the fluorescent dyes.

252 Plasma membrane integrity of the three treatments was assessed by
253 double-staining with SYBR-14 (for live cell nucleic acid staining - Thermo Fisher)
254 propidium iodide (PI, for dead cell nucleic acid staining that penetrates through
255 damaged plasma membrane - Thermo Fisher), adapted from the method
256 proposed by (Hagedorn et al., 2009), with modifications. In brief, for each
257 treatment, pellets were mixed with 0.25 μ L SYBR-14 (0.02 mM) and incubated in
258 the dark at room temperature for 4 min. After, 1.0 μ L PI (1.19 mM) was added to
259 the samples, which were incubated for 1 min, also in the dark and at room
260 temperature. After final incubation, the samples were diluted (1:10) in Ginsburg
261 solution and analyzed on flow cytometry.

262 Fluorescence signals of SYBR-14, gathered via 533/30 nm band-pass
263 filter, and PI, gathered via 670 nm long-pass filter, were plotted on logarithmic
264 scales. The sperm population was gated referring to the expected forward- and
265 side-scatter signals. Ten thousand events per sample were acquired, the
266 percentage of intact cells (positive for SYBR and negative for IP) was recorded.

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268 **2.7.3. Sperm morphology**

269 One hundred microliters of the milt previously fixed in saline-buffered
270 formaldehyde was mixed with 10 μ L of Rose Bengal dye (Magnotti et al., 2018;
271 Streit Jr et al., 2004). The adapted methodology includes conformation of the

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272 slides per drained drop, placing three drops of 10 μ L, each, on a histological slide.
273 The slides were performed per drained drop, with a volume of 10 μ L per drop.
274 The morphology evaluated were (Milorini et al., 2011; da Costa et al., 2020):
275 Normal spermatozoa, short tail, distally curled tail, strongly curled tail, broken tail,
276 folded tail, degenerate head, macrocephaly, microcephaly, loose head, proximal
277 gout, distal gout (Fig. 2). The slides were read with the 100 x objective, using
278 immersion oil. In total, two hundred sperm were counted per slide.

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280 [Fig. 2. here]

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282 **2.7.4. Mitochondrial activity**

283 Mitochondrial activity was assessed using the MTT test (Liu et al., 1997).
284 MTT reduction assay was adapted of Aziz, (2006), with modifications. In short,
285 after thawing of the control treatment, two hundred microliters of milt sample were
286 centrifuged only once (1000 X g for 10 min), in order to concentrate the
287 spermatozoa from the cell suspension, forming a pellet as explained above. For
288 all treatments the pellet was resuspended in 400 μ L of MTT (Invitrogen[®], Thermo
289 Fisher Scientific) stock solution (5 mg of MTT/mL of PBS) and were placed into
290 a 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube. The suspension was incubated in an oven for 2 h at 28
291 $^{\circ}$ C. After incubation, all tubes were centrifuged (1000 X g for 5 min). The
292 supernatant was discarded, and the sedimentation was strongly resuspended in
293 400 μ L of dimethyl sulfoxide (Me_2SO) with the help of a pipette. Finally, eight
294 wells of the 96-well microplate were used, for each treatment. The absorbance
295 analysis was performed on a Spectrophotometer (SpectraMax[®] M2 250
296 Microplate Readers), at the wavelengths of 570 and 630 nm. The absorbance
297 level was calculated by the difference between both wavelengths, and the final
298 value was adjusted for 100 million sperm.

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300 **2.7.5. Fertility assessment**

301 Oocytes obtained after hormonal induction with ECP were used in equal
302 quantities (85 ± 7 oocytes) and they were mixed with a volume of milt indicated
303 for each treatment (control: 3.50 μ L, T1: 6.26 μ L, and T2: 92.01 μ L). The
304 inseminating dose (Bombardelli et al., 2006) was calculated from the sperm
305 concentration and the percentage of motile sperm, allowing a total of 70,000

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306 sperm per oocyte (Neumann et al., 2019). The quantity of oocytes to be fertilized
307 was measured with the help of an insulin syringe (1 mL). Then the tip of the
308 syringe was cut off, and 0.1 mL of oocytes were measured. Each portion of
309 oocytes were individually placed in plastic cups (10 mL) and the volume of milt
310 was added. The activation of the milt and hydration of the oocytes was carried
311 out with 5 mL of distilled water and gentle mixing for one minute. The incubation
312 was carried out in fine mesh plastic strainers, kept in 500 L plastic tanks, with
313 constant control of the water temperature (24 °C) and oxygen feeding.

314 The embryonic survival rate was performed between eight (initiates
315 blastopore formation begins) to ten hours (blastopore closing forming germination
316 ring) after fertilization of the oocyte. Thirty-eight hours later fertilization the
317 hatching rate was measured from the total embryos that survived. Was
318 considered the number of normal (larvae without any abnormality in the spine,
319 yolk sac, or head) or deformed larvae (Jeziarska et al., 2009). These analyzes
320 were carried out in a stereoscopic microscope (10 x objective).

321

322 2.8. Statistical methodology

323 The data obtained in treatments applied to cryopreserved milt were
324 subjected to normality tests (Shapiro-Wilk) and Bartlett's homogeneity. When
325 necessary, data were transformed (LOG) and outliers were excluded when
326 present. The data showing normal distribution were analyzed using one-way
327 analysis of variance (One-Way ANOVA), and when a significant difference was
328 observed, the treatments were compared using the Tukey test. The results
329 analyzed by means of parametric analyzes are presented in bar graphs using the
330 mean and standard deviation (SD). Nonparametric data were analyzed using
331 Kruskal-Wallis analysis, and when differences were observed, treatments were
332 compared using the Dunn test. The data analyzed by means of non-parametric
333 analysis are presented in Box and Whiskers graphs (maximum and minimum).
334 Statistical analysis was performed using Statistical Analysis System - (SAS) v.9.0
335 software and GraphPad Prism 7.0.

336

337 3. Results

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339 The results showed that the differential centrifugation (T1), presented a
340 better percentage of motility compared to the control treatment ($42.58 \pm 6.05\%$
341 and $32.44 \pm 6.033\%$, respectively, $P = 0.0427$, Fig. 3A). The motility time (Fig.
342 3B) was shorter for the centrifugal treatment by density gradient (T2, 32.38 ± 0.92
343 s) than for treatment T1 (36.69 ± 3.62 s), $P = 0.0072$.

344 Membrane integrity was not different between treatments (Fig. 3C). The
345 percentages of integral membrane for each treatment were: control= $72.96 \pm$
346 7.30% , T1= $79.56 \pm 6.35\%$ and T2= $76.27 \pm 4.16\%$. The presence of normal
347 sperm (Fig. 3D) was higher in T2 when compared to the control and T1
348 treatments. The values obtained were $10.72 \pm 3.53\%$, $3.97 \pm 1.95\%$ and $13.55 \pm$
349 5.82% , for the control groups, T1 and T2, respectively.

350 The T1 and T2 treatments were different from the control treatment in the
351 MTT test (Fig. 3E, $P = 0.0007$). The control group showed MTT values of $0.20 \pm$
352 0.08 AU/100 million spz, meanwhile the centrifuged treatments resulted in values
353 of 1.58 ± 0.79 AU/100 million spz (T1) and 2.02 ± 1.88 AU/100 million spz (T2).

354 The decrease in sperm concentration was evident in T2 ($2.79 \times 10^8 \pm$
355 1.71×10^8 cells/mL, Fig. 3F) compared to the control treatment ($5.01 \times 10^9 \pm$
356 1.03×10^9 cells/mL) ($P < 0.0001$), but it was not different from T1 ($2.35 \times 10^9 \pm$
357 7.11×10^8 cells/mL).

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359 [Fig. 3. here]

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361 The sperm kinetics parameters measured did not show differences
362 between the treatments (Table 2).

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364 [Table 2 here]

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366 Regarding tail damage, T1 represented the lowest rate (Fig. 4A, $P <$
367 0.0001). However, this treatment was the one that represented a greater portion
368 of spermatozoa with a damaged head (Fig. 4B, $P < 0.0001$). Finally, there was
369 no difference ($P = 0.7473$) between the treatments for sperm damage due to the
370 presence of gout (Fig. 4C).

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372 [Fig. 4. here]

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374 The sperm morphology of silver catfish after thawing and differential and
375 gradient centrifugation can be seen in Table 3.

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377 [Table 3 here]

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379 For tail abnormalities, we observed that the control treatment had a higher
380 percentage of folded tail ($P < 0.0001$), short tail ($P < 0.0001$) and broken tail ($P <$
381 0.0001) than treatments T1 and T2. The strong curled tail was higher ($P < 0.0001$)
382 in T2 treatment when compared to T1 and control. For the distally curled tail, a
383 higher percentage ($P = 0.0459$) was observed in T2 treatment when compared
384 to T1.

385 For head damage, we observed a difference ($P < 0.0001$) between
386 treatments with the highest percentage of loose head for treatment T1, followed
387 by T2 and the control with the lowest percentage. We observed a higher ($P <$
388 0.0001) percentage of sperm with macrocephaly in the control treatment,
389 compared to T1 and T2, while the percentage of microcephaly was higher ($P =$
390 0.0002) in T1, when compared to the control and T2. The percentage of sperm
391 with degenerated head did not differ ($P = 0.3311$) between treatments.

392 We observed no difference between treatments for the percentage of
393 proximal cytoplasmic gout ($P = 0.6574$) and distal cytoplasmic gout ($P = 0.3053$).

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395 [Fig. 5. here]

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397 Regarding the embryo survival rate (Fig. 5A) and hatching (Fig. 5B), when
398 the centrifugation was applied in the milt, the results were superior to the control
399 ($P < 0.0001$). The embryonic survival for the control treatment was $40.03 \pm$
400 11.67% , $76.68 \pm 15.22\%$ (T1), and $69.85 \pm 17.85\%$ (T2). On the other hand, the
401 hatching rate for the three treatments was $24.14 \pm 13.97\%$, $54.62 \pm 17.39\%$ and
402 $50.87 \pm 20.59\%$, respectively. Regarding the presence of normal larvae (Fig. 5C),
403 no difference was obtained between treatments ($P = 0.4336$).

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4. Discussion

In the present study, AllGrad 90% density gradient centrifugation was compared for the first time with differential centrifugation to separate thawed milt from fish. Thus, it was possible to identify that both centrifugation techniques benefited in obtaining a portion of sperm of better quality based on the results obtained, especially in the rates of embryonic survival and hatching, which were certainly related to the combination of indices such as the percentage and the time of motility and consequently with mitochondrial activity. In this context, the separation of spermatozoa by differential or density gradient centrifugation can be considered promising techniques in induced reproduction programs, as auxiliary tools for the cryopreservation of fish milt.

Although statistically there was no difference between the differential centrifugation with the other treatments and the results obtained for the sperm concentration, it was possible to show that the centrifugation techniques influenced the number of cells obtained since the average value of the differential centrifugation was lower than the control treatment is greater than the density gradient centrifugation. An explanation for this is that differential centrifugation is a method that can quickly eliminate many undesired components from a large amount of starting material, normally this method is prior to density gradient centrifugation and is used for greater purification of samples (Griffith, 2010). The above leads us to think that during the differential centrifugation, in addition to eliminating a large amount of cryoprotectant, sperm cells of lower density are also eliminated. On the other hand, the density gradient acts as a “molecular sieve”, therefore, the larger or less dense particles will remain trapped along the gradient, finally allowing the sedimentation of the heavier cells and with sufficient size to cross these gradients (Rivers et al., 2020).

Sperm motility is a fundamental index to estimate sperm quality (Lassen et al., 2021) and it has been reported that it has a high correlation with the fertilization or hatching rates (Gallego et al., 2018). In general, after cryopreservation, a lower percentage of sperm cells with motility is observed (Lassen et al., 2021). Our results showed that the milt samples that were subjected to differential centrifugation presented 10.14% more motile sperm than the control treatment and no difference in the percentage of mobile cells between the centrifugation techniques. These results allow us to infer about the efficiency

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439 of the centrifugation techniques in obtaining spermatozoa with better quality after
440 the thawing of fish milt. Other studies have also shown the benefit of sperm
441 separation from cryopreserved milt. Li et al. (2010) showed that samples of
442 cryopreserved milt of the species *C. carpio* separated by density gradient
443 presented high motility compared to non-separated sperm (Li et al., 2010).
444 Additionally, Horokhovatskyi et al. (2018) reported a high percentage of sperm
445 motility after separating with density gradients when using milt of the *A. ruthenus*
446 (Horokhovatskyi et al., 2018). Another study carried out with *S. salar*, showed
447 that when using a density gradient of 45%/90%, the percentage of mobile cells
448 increased by 5.8% compared to the control treatment (Bravo et al., 2020).

449 Our results also showed the positive effect of centrifugation on the duration
450 of motility, especially differential separation. Motility is mediated by different
451 factors, for example, the correct functioning of the mitochondria (Cabrita et al.,
452 2014; Sandoval-Vargas et al., 2021). The presence of cryoprotectant in the
453 control treatment samples probably led to the inhibition of the electron transport
454 chain (complexes I and II) by reducing oxygen consumption, related to an
455 alteration in intracellular energy levels (in ATP form), and so on mitochondrial
456 functionality (Figuroa et al., 2019), ultimately resulting in reduced motility time.

457 A greater selection of viable sperm in a milt sample is an important factor
458 for the success of assisted reproductive techniques. Herein lies the importance
459 of selection techniques, which allow the use of viable sperm with a relatively
460 higher fertilization capacity (Horokhovatskyi et al., 2018), which certainly justifies
461 the use of the centrifugation technique. Our results did not show differences
462 between the percentage of viable cells or cells with an intact membrane for the
463 different treatments. In the *A. ruthenus*, the percentage of viable sperm was
464 26.5% higher when comparing separated cryopreserved milt samples with
465 samples that were not separated (Horokhovatskyi et al., 2018). These results
466 lead us to consider two possibilities. The first of these refers to the specific
467 characteristics of fish sperm, such as osmolality or ionic composition in the
468 surrounding medium, which vary between species or even within the same
469 species (Tiersch, 2008; Horokhovatskyi et al., 2018) or by the presence of sperm
470 structures such as the acrosome, present in the spermatozoa of the *A. ruthenus*
471 (Li et al., 2009). The second possibility is related to the differential centrifugation,
472 performed in the present study to the control treatment at the time of applying the

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473 membrane integrity analysis protocol. This process could positively influence the
474 presence of viable sperm in this treatment, leading it to not be different from the
475 other treatments. Therefore, the benefits of using centrifugation as an auxiliary
476 tool in milt cryopreservation are again evident.

477 The increase in the number of sperm abnormalities is related to the loss of
478 motility and consequently with the fertilization capacity after cryopreservation (da
479 Costa et al., 2019). The results obtained show that the density gradient
480 centrifugation method allowed to obtain a larger portion of normal sperm, but not
481 for differential separation. However, both centrifugation methods were mainly
482 represented by a greater number of loose heads. These results may be related
483 to the centrifugation process when considering what Herman (1994) said. This
484 author reports that the presence of abnormalities such as loose head are due to
485 the manipulation of milt (Herman, 1994). However, in practice, *in vitro*
486 reproduction in fish is carried out by a gentle mixing of gametes after being
487 hydrated (oocytes) and activated (spermatozoa). This procedure leads us to
488 propose the hypothesis that spermatozoa with a loose head, but which are
489 apparently viable, coincide with the micropyle of the oocyte, fertilizing it and,
490 evolving towards embryonic development and consequently obtaining free-living
491 embryos. In that sense, it is necessary to carry out future studies to verify this
492 approach. On the other hand, the thawed milt samples that were not centrifuged
493 presented abnormalities mainly broken tail and macrocephaly. Macrocephaly
494 was one of the reduced anomalies after centrifuging cryopreserved samples; this
495 malformation was negatively correlated (-0,88) with sperm quality parameters
496 such as motility (da Costa et al., 2019). Dead and sperm with abnormal
497 morphology as well as sperm debris may be an obstacle to successful fertilization
498 in *in vitro* conditions (Poe-Zeigler et al., 1997). Unlike fish, in mammals the
499 assessment of sperm morphological changes is considered an important
500 parameter (Streit Jr et al., 2004).

501 The functioning of sperm cells and their metabolic activity is dependent on
502 the mitochondria and its components, such as proteins (Sandoval-Vargas et al.,
503 2021). This organelle is the main source of energy and cellular homeostasis
504 (Cabrita et al., 2014) and are very vulnerable to low temperature stress (Tsvetkov
505 and Naydenova, 1987), so validating its functionality after cryopreservation is
506 very important. The mitochondrial dehydrogenase enzyme, present in the

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507 mitochondrial membrane, it is in charge of reducing MTT to thiazolyl blue
508 tetrazolium bromide, however, enzyme only acts when the cell is viable (Riss et
509 al., 2004; Liu and Nair, 2010). In our study, it was found that the centrifuged
510 treatments presented greater mitochondrial functionality than the control,
511 coinciding with the results found in the study by Bravo et al. (2020). In this study,
512 carried out with cryopreserved milt from *S. salar*, it was shown that the samples
513 that were separated by a density gradient resulted in a higher percentage of
514 membrane potential than the control treatment. Although the membrane potential
515 was not assessed in our study, this variable is considered to be a measure that
516 indicates mitochondrial functionality (Angrimani et al., 2015). Therefore,
517 centrifugation techniques applied to cryopreserved fish milt can be suggested as
518 a potential biotechnological tool to improve reproductive efficiency in species of
519 commercial or biological interest (Figueroa et al., 2019). However, future MTT
520 tests for milt thawed after centrifugation could be recommended in order to obtain
521 other explanations considering the possibility of latent injuries (Sherman, 1967).

522 The success of artificial reproduction, based on cryopreservation
523 programs, depends on the maximum use of available gametes, which means
524 fertilizing the largest number of oocytes with the least amount of sperm
525 (Bombardelli et al., 2006). Additionally, the use of selection techniques is of great
526 importance since it allows concentrating spermatozoa that maintain the
527 fertilization capacity (Horokhovatskyi et al., 2018). For the present study, the
528 sperm of the milt samples that were centrifuged showed better embryonic survival
529 and hatching rates. Cabrita et al. (2014) indicated that the best determinant of
530 sperm quality is not only the ability of sperm to fertilize an oocyte, but also to
531 contribute to the initial embryonic development. A review carried out for aquatic
532 species reported that high fertilization rates in artificial reproduction should be
533 greater than 70% to 80%, depending on the species (Beirão et al., 2019).
534 Considering these values, we could assume that from the differential
535 centrifugation it was possible to obtain high fertilization rates positively influencing
536 the embryonic survival, which was 36.36% higher when compared to the control
537 treatment. Finally, although no differences were found in the percentage of
538 normal larvae, a future study that includes monitoring their growth would be very
539 interesting, considering that the growth of the offspring may be affected by the
540 use of cryopreserved sperm in induced reproduction routines (Nusbaumer et al.,

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541 2019). The previous placement, part of the fact that the present study allowed to
542 identify that the negative effects generated by cryopreservation can be reduced
543 when using the sperm separation method.

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545 **5. Conclusion**

546 In conclusion, the centrifugation techniques applied to the cryopreserved
547 semen of *R. quelen* made it possible to obtain a portion of better quality sperm
548 because they finally allowed a high percentage of live embryos to be obtained,
549 which is added to a higher percentage of larvae that hatched. In this sense, the
550 adaptation of these biotechnologies as auxiliary tools for the cryopreservation of
551 fish milt of biological interest or for aquaculture is recommended. However, in
552 practical terms, differential separation could have some advantages over density
553 gradient centrifugation if one considers the ease of implementation of the method
554 compared to gradient coformation, in addition to the fact that this technique also
555 allowed, for this species, obtain spermatozoa with a longer motility time.

556

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564

565 **Conflicts of interest**

566 We declare that have no competing financial interests or personal
567 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this
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825 **Table 1.** Summary of the treatments applied to cryopreserved milt of catfish (*Rhamdia*
826 *quelen*)

Treatment	Description
Control	Milt samples thawed and not centrifuged*
Differential centrifugation (T1)	Thawed milt diluted in Ginsburg extender solution (1:2) and centrifuged at 1000 X g for 10 min at 4 °C. The formed pellet was resuspended in 200 µL of Ginsburg and again centrifuged (500 X g for 5 min at 4 °C). The pellet was resuspended in 150 µL of Ginsburg, the sample used to perform the different analyses.
Density gradient centrifugation (T2)	Thawed milt, placed at the end of the density gradient formed with two layers of different densities of AllGrad 90% (90% and 45%), each layer with the same volume (100 µL). Afterwards, a first centrifugation was performed at 1000 X g for 10 min at 4 °C. The formed pellet was resuspended in 200 µL of Ginsburg and again centrifuged (500 X g for 5 min at 4 °C). The final pellet was resuspended in 150 µL of Ginsburg, the sample used to perform the different analyses.

827 * For the measurements of membrane integrity and mitochondrial activity, a single centrifugation
828 (1000 X g/10 min) was performed for the control treatment samples due to the need to have
829 concentrated cells and not in suspension.

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Table 2. Sperm kinetic parameters of catfish (*Rhamdia quelen*)

Variables	Treatments			P-value
	Control	T1	T2	
VCL ($\mu\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)	65.32±10.22	71.28±5.97	73.31±5.20	0.1084*
VAP($\mu\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)	46.55±9.69	50.85±6.30	51.06±3.28	0.3594**
VSL ($\mu\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)	44.37±9.17	48.51±6.20	48.48±3.19	0.3764**
STR (%)	95.22±0.55	95.32±0.58	94.87±0.89	0.4114*
WOB (%)	70.69±4.20	71.26±5.33	69.68±3.94	0.7816*
PROG (μm)	692.8±150.6	759.0±94.79	772.4±51.15	0.3009**
BCF (Hz)	37.17±2.26	36.35±1.57	35.63±2.73	0.9506*

832 Mean ± Standard deviation. Sperm kinetic parameters of catfish (*Rhamdia quelen*) cryopreserved

833 milt after control (thawed and non-centrifuged milt), T1 (thawed and differential centrifugation milt

834 at 1000 X g for 10 min) and T2 (thawed and density gradient centrifugation milt at 1000 X g for

835 10 min) treatments were applied. *Analysis of variance. **Kruskal-Wallis analysis. n = 8.

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Table 3. Sperm morphological parameters of catfish (*Rhamdia quelen*)

Variables	Treatments			P-value
	Control	T1	T2	
Distally curled tail (%)	1.53±0.76ab	1.38±0.70b	2.71±1.83a	0.0459**
Broken tail (%)	17.03±4.75a	9.94±3.35b	10.09±2.75b	< 0.0001**
Folded tail (%)	8.72±2.81a	3.84±1.73b	4.89±1.98b	< 0.0001*
Strongly curled tail (%)	4.09±1.62b	4.34±2.50b	12.31±5.99a	< 0.0001**
Short tail (%)	14.50±3.35a	7.41±2.91b	7.48±2.79b	< 0.0001*
Loose head (%)	14.28±4.23c	53.34±10.65a	33.22±14.06b	< 0.0001**
Macrocephaly (%)	16.91±4.14a	3.34±1.40b	3.77±1.91b	< 0.0001**
Microcephaly (%)	0.97±0.56b	3.13±1.95a	1.50±0.94b	0.0002**
Degenerate Head (%)	3.56±1.17	2.78±1.82	3.41±1.61	0.3311*
Proximal gout (%)	2.75±1.10	2.72±1.98	2.65±1.69	0.6574**
Distal gout (%)	4.94±1.91	3.81±1.46	4.43±2.60	0.3053*

838 Mean ± Standard deviation. Sperm kinetic parameters of catfish (*Rhamdia quelen*) cryopreserved
839 milt after control (thawed and non-centrifuged milt), T1 (thawed and differential centrifugation milt
840 at 1000 X g for 10 min) and T2 (thawed and density gradient centrifugation milt at 1000 X g for
841 10 min) treatments were applied. *Analysis of variance. **Kruskal-Wallis analysis. Different letters
842 indicate difference between treatments. n = 16.

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845

846 **Fig. 1.** Experimental design to compare two centrifugation techniques [differential centrifugation
847 (T1) and centrifugation with AllGrade 90% (T2)] applied to cryopreserved catfish (*Rhamdia*
848 *quelen*) milt. After the conformation of the milt *pool* (N=11 males) and before its cryopreservation,
849 the quality of the *pool* was validated by means of sperm concentration, sperm motility percentage
850 and sperm morphology (percentage of normal sperm). The straws were randomly divided into
851 three treatments (control, differential and gradient). The same parameters were evaluated for
852 each treatment: sperm concentration (n=8), motility and kinetic parameters (n=8), membrane
853 integrity (n=8), sperm morphology (n=8, in duplicate), mitochondrial activity (n=8) embryo survival
854 (n=8, in duplicate) and hatching, where n corresponds to the number of straws.

855

856 **Fig. 2.** Some morphological abnormalities of catfish (*Rhamdia quelen*) sperm. a) Normal sperm,
857 b) Broken tail, c) Folded tail, d) Loose head, e) Macrocephaly, f) Micricephaly, g) Distal gout and
858 h) Short tail. Magnification level 5 μ m.

859

860 **Fig. 1.** Sperm quality of catfish (*Rhamdia quelen*) cryopreserved milt after control (thawed and
861 non-centrifuged milt), T1 (thawed and differential centrifugation milt at 1000 X g for 10 min) and
862 T2 (thawed and density gradient centrifugation milt at 1000 X g for 10 min) treatments were
863 applied. A) Motility (P = 0.0427; n = 8); B) Motility time (P = 0.0072; n = 8); C) Membrane Integrity
864 (p = 0.1190; n = 8); D) Normal spermatozoa (P < 0.0001; n = 16); MTT (P = 0.0007; n = 8); F)
865 Sperm concentration (P < 0.0001; n = 8). Analysis of variance followed by Tukey test (Figure A
866 and C). Kruskal-Wallis analysis followed by Dunn's test (Figures B, D, E and F). Different letters
867 indicate difference between treatments.

868

869 **Fig.4.** Spermatozoa morphological damage of catfish (*Rhamdia quelen*) cryopreserved milt after
870 control (thawed and non-centrifuged milt), T1 (thawed and differential centrifugation milt at 1000
871 X g for 10 min) and T2 (thawed and density gradient centrifugation milt at 1000 X g for 10 min)
872 treatments were applied. A) Total tail damage (P < 0.0001; n = 16); B) Total head damage (P <
873 0.0001; n = 16); C) Total gout damage (P = 0.7473; n = 16). Analysis of variance followed by
874 Tukey's test (Figures C). Kruskal-Wallis analysis followed by Dunn's test (Figures A and B).
875 Different letters indicate difference between treatments.

876

877 **Fig. 5.** Embryo survival, hatch rate and normal larvae of catfish (*Rhamdia quelen*) cryopreserved
878 milt after control (thawed and non-centrifuged milt), T1 (thawed and differential centrifugation milt
879 at 1000 X g for 10 min) and T2 (thawed and density gradient centrifugation milt at 1000 X g for
880 10 min) treatments were applied. A) Embryonic survival rate (P < 0.0001; n = 16); B) Hatch rate
881 (P < 0.0001; n = 16); C) Normal larvae (P = 0.4336; n = 16). Analysis of variance followed by
882 Tukey's test (Figures A and B). Kruskal-Wallis analysis followed by Dunn's test (Figure C).
883 Different letters indicate difference between treatments.

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